

Sensory Profile of *Xanthosoma sagittifolium* (Kontomire), an Indigenous Green Leafy Vegetable in Ghana

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Executive Summary

This report provides a comprehensive sensory profile for processed indigenous green leafy vegetables, focusing on Kontomire leaves. Indigenous green leafy vegetables are vital components of diets in tropical Africa, valued for their nutritional, functional, and aesthetic contributions. However, preservation challenges limit their availability during dry seasons. The project aimed to develop a sensory profile to enhance understanding and utilization of processed Kontomire. Samples of Kontomire leaves were processed using boiling and blanching methods and evaluated for sensory attributes such as appearance, aroma, texture-in-hand, flavour, mouthfeel, and aftertaste. A trained sensory panel employed Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA®), involving term generation, consensus building, and intensity scaling, to identify and quantify 60 descriptive attributes. Evaluation utilized a 10-point category scale, with randomized sample presentation for accuracy. Statistical analyses, including ANOVA and Tukey's HSD, were conducted to identify significant differences in sensory attributes. This work lays the foundation for further exploration of processing techniques to enhance the preservation and sensory appeal of indigenous green leafy vegetables.

Introduction

Green leafy vegetables form part of the diet of most people of tropical Africa (Ejoh et al., 2017). Many people in tropical Africa depend largely on a large number of green leafy vegetables as sources of minerals and vitamins (Ilelaboye et al., 2013). They contain substantial quantities of minerals like iron, calcium, phosphorus, potassium, magnesium and zinc (Ejoh et al., 2007). Indigenous green leafy vegetables are inexpensive and easily accessible. They are also easy to cook, provide roughage and are rich in antioxidants and other health related phytochemicals (Kamga et al., 2013; Orech et al., 2005). Besides their nutritional benefits, they add flavour, variety, taste, colour and aesthetic appeal to what would otherwise be a monotonous diet. They are in abundance shortly after the rainy season but become scarce during the dry season. In Africa indigenous green leafy vegetables are rarely processed, presumably due to the general lack of basic preservation facilities for freezing, canning or dehydration (Mepba et al., 2007). A wide variety of indigenous green leafy vegetable species consumed in Ghana include Aleefu, Ayoyo, Bitter Leaf, Borkorborkor, Kontomire, Gboma, Dandelion and amongst others. As part of a project, Senlab has decided to provide a profile for various processed indigenous green leafy vegetables as possible. The profile would contain attribute names, their definitions, references and intensity scores for all necessary modalities.

Objective:

To develop a sensory profile for processed indigenous green leafy vegetables (Kontomire).

Environmental Controls

All assessments were conducted at University of Ghana, Sensory Evaluation Laboratory. The laboratory is purpose built and equipped for sensory testing. The laboratory has a preparation area, discussion area, and individually partitioned tasting booths for assessors. The lab was well-lit with natural white light from white LED bulbs and a constant temperature of $27^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ maintained by an air-conditioner. An extractor fan to eliminate any unwanted odours was also installed. The laboratory was designed to minimize distractions from noise and human activity, providing an ideal environment for concentrated work. Samples were served through hatches behind a closed partition to minimize direct interaction between assessors and researcher.

Assessors

Nine (9) screened and trained panellists were used to assess the samples. They were screened based on their ability to identify the basic tests, recognise different odours, rank intensities of a basic taste, discriminate and tell differences between samples and their ability to describe foods. The assessors used for this test passed these basic requirements and were hence recruited.

Methodology

Sample details

Fresh kontomire leaves were obtained from a backyard garden Lashibi. The leaves were subjected to two different cooking processes: Boiling and blanching. Samples upon reception were stored in a clear polythene bag and kept in the refrigerator until ready for assessment.

Table 1: Table giving details on the Dandelion leaves used for the test

Location	Date harvested	Date bought	Date assessed
Lashibi	Tuesday, 19 th November, 2024	-	Tuesday, 19 th November, 2024

Samples assessed

#	Treatment	Sample code
1	Raw Kontomire leaves	123
2	Boiled Kontomire leaves	209
3	Blanched Kontomire leaves	490

Pictures of different levels of cooked dandelion leaves

Sample preparation

Fresh Kontomire leaves were divided into three sections, each measuring approximately 4–6 mm. The leaves were finely chopped using a knife and cutting board. A 30 g portion of the chopped leaves was weighed and washed in three steps. The first wash, using only water, removed physical impurities. The second wash, with water and salt, reduced microbial load. The final rinse removed any residual salt.

Blanching preparation

A saucepan containing 1500 ml of water was heated to 95°C. The 30 g sample of prepared Kontomire leaves was added to the boiling water and blanched for 10 minutes. After blanching, the leaves were immediately cooled in iced water for 2 minutes before being prepared for assessment.

Boiling preparation

A separate 1500 ml of water was placed in a saucepan, and 30 g of the Kontomire leaves were added. The water and leaves were brought to a boil, with the cooking time starting once heating began. The leaves were boiled for 30 minutes, then cooled to room temperature before being served for sensory evaluation.

Sample serving

Each panellist was provided with 2g of the raw and 2 parts of the blanched and boiled Kontomire. The samples were served in 80cc cups with lids. They assessed the appearance, aroma, texture-in-hand, flavour, mouthfeel, and aftertaste. Samples were served in a monadic sequential order. During evaluation, a complete block randomized presentation order design based on Williams's Latin Squares design in Compusense Inc (Guelph, Ontario, Canada) was used. Water was provided as a palate cleanser.

Assessment protocol

The test involved four main activities: term generation, consensus building, scale and attribute training, and evaluation.

Term generation required each panellist to assess the products and develop attributes or terms that accurately and completely described each sample for all sensory modalities; appearance, aroma, flavour, mouth feel and aftertaste. They

defined these attributes and allocated anchors while providing references as necessary to clarify ambiguous terms.

Consensus building involved all the panellists coming together to agree on a final list of descriptors that accurately described the various almond nut samples. Reference products were provided where needed to clarify ambiguous descriptors and align panel agreement. Scale training involved each panellist allocating intensity scores for each attribute per sample on a 10cm line. To improve scoring, they collectively agreed on the ranges of each attribute per product, to help ensure they used the scale in a similar way and established the rank order of the products.

In evaluation, each panellist assessed each sample and allocated a score to each attribute on a 10cm line scale, with 0 indicating that the attribute was "*not intense*", and 10 indicating that it was "*very intense*". The assessment was conducted in duplicates, with panellists evaluating the samples one after the other in a randomized order achieved using Williams Latin Square design as set out in Compusense (Williams, 1949). Panellists rinsed their palates with water between tastings, and a forced break of 30 seconds was allowed after each sample was tasted. A five-minute session break was forced between replicate sessions. Panel performance analysis was conducted on the trial assessment to check for agreement among assessors. The final evaluation was conducted in triplicate using Compusense Inc (Guelph, Ontario, Canada).

Statistical analysis

Mean intensity scores obtained from Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA®) were determined. Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) (Samples x Assessor) was done for each attribute for QDA® data. Tukey's HSD post hoc analysis was further carried

out to explain where sample differences in the products were. The statistical analysis was performed using the MINITAB v.17.0 software package (Minitab Inc,UK).

RESULTS

Descriptor List

The Kontomire leaves were observed to consist of two distinct parts: the leafy portion and the thick mid-rib. As a result, assessments for the sensory modalities—appearance, texture-in-hand, flavour, mouthfeel, and aftertaste—were conducted for each part.

A total of **60** attributes were used to describe the samples across all modalities. Table 2 shows the descriptive attributes used, their definitions, and anchors for scoring on intensity scales and Table 3 shows the protocol for assessing the attributes.

Table 2: Attribute names, definitions, references and anchors developed for cooked kontomire samples across all modalities.

Modality	Descriptor	Definition	Anchor
Appearance (Leafy part)	Olive green	Sample has a colour like that of the olive fruit	Light to Dark
	Forest green	Sample has a forest green colour	Light to Dark
	Dull	Sample lacks a shiny surface	Not to very
	Mid-rib	Sample has a mid-rib	Present/ not present
	Soggy	Sample appears moist and soft	Not to very
	Vein-like structures	Presence of vein-like structures on both sides of the sample	Present / not present
	Delicate	Sample looks soft and gives the impression it will tear when a little force is applied	Not to very
	Translucent	Sample partially allows light to pass through	Not to very
	Cooked	Sample appears to have undergone some form of boiling	Not to very
	Smooth surface	The surface of the sample gives the impression it will be smooth when touched with the fingers	Not to very
	Waxy	Sample has a rubbery look	Not to very
	Rough bottom	Backside of sample appears it will feel rough when touched	Smooth - Rough
	Opaque	Sample does not allow light to pass through	Not - Very

	Thin	Sample appears flat, lightweight and flexible	Thick - Thin
	Fresh	Sample gives the impression of being newly harvested	Old - Fresh
	Yellow patches	Presence of yellow patches on the surface of the leaf	Present / Not present
	Purple margin	Sample has a purple coloured edge all around	Present / Not present
	Grey streaks	Presence of grey lines on the surface of the sample	Present / Not present
	Dry	Sample appears to lack moisture on its surface	Not - Very
	Black spots	Presence of black spots on the surface of the sample	Present / Not present
	Brown spots	Presence of brown spots on the surface of the sample	Present / Not present
Appearance (Mid-rib)	Olive green	Sample has a colour like that of the olive fruit	Light to Dark
	Green	Sample has a green colour	Light to Dark
	Juicy	Sample gives the impression that it will contain some moisture in it	Not to very
	Soft	Sample appears easy to bite on	Frim to soft
	Smooth surface	The surface of the sample gives the impression it will be smooth when touched with the fingers	Not to very

Aroma	Cooked yam	Aroma like that of cooked pona yam	Not to very
	Seashore	Aroma associated with distinctive fish odour, seaweed and ocean	Not to very
	Boiled Kontomire	Characteristic smell of boiled kontomire	Not to very
	Sharp smell	Sample has a sharp smell	Not to very
	Boiled maize	Characteristic smell of boiled maize on the cob	Not to very
	Metallic	Sample smells like that of rusted metal	Not to very
	Ad)de	Characteristic smell of fresh ad)de	Not to very
	Grassy	Characteristic aroma of freshly cut grass	Not - Very
	Water-melon rind	Characteristic aroma of watermelon rind	Not - Very
	Kontomire	Characteristic smell of fresh kontomire leaves	Not - Very
	Sugarcane	Characteristic smell of sugarcane	Not - Very
	Turkey berry	Sample smells like that of uncooked turkey berries	Not - Very
	Starfruit	Characteristic smell of unripe star fruit	Not - Very
Plantain leaf	Sample smells like that of a plantain leaf	Not - Very	
Flavour (Leafy part)	Kontomire	Sample tastes like that of cooked kontomire	Not to very
			Not to very
Mouthfeel (Leafy part)	Juicy	Sample releases moisture in the mouth when chewed	Not to very

	Chewy	Sample needs to be chewed for a while before swallowing	Not to very
	Smooth	Sample has an even feel in the mouth	Not to very
	Soft	Sample is easy to chew and easily disintegrates in the mouth	Not to very
Mouthfeel (Mid-rib)	Itchy feel	Sample causes irritation in the mouth when chewing	Not to very
	Soft	Sample is easy to bite through	Not to very
Aftertaste (Leafy part)	Itchy feel	Lingering irritating sensation in the mouth and tongue after swallowing	Not to very
	Residue	Presence of particles in the mouth after swallowing	Not to very
Aftertaste (Mid-rib)	Itchy feel	Lingering irritating sensation in the mouth and tongue after swallowing	Not to very
Texture-in-hand (Leafy part)	Rubbery	Sample feels like of rubber between the fingers	Not to very
	Soft	Sample has a soft feel and breaks easily when rubbed	Not to very
	Firm	Sample has a rigid feel and does not break easily when rubbed	Not to very
	Moist	Sample leaves moisture on the fingers when rubbed	Not to very

	Rough bottom	Underside of the sample has an uneven feel when rubbed with the fingers	Not to very
	Smooth surface	Surface of sample has an even feel on the fingers when rubbed	Not to very
Texture-in-hand (Mid-rib)	Slimy	Sample releases a viscous, sippery substance when pressed between the fingers	Not to very
	Soft	Sample has a soft feel and breaks easily when rubbed	Not to very
	Juicy	Sample releases moisture when pressed between the fingers	Not to very
	Smooth	Sample has an even feel when rubbed with the fingers	Not to very
	Firm	Samples feels rigid and not easily compressible	Not to very

Table 3: Protocol used to assess the samples.

Modality	Protocol
Appearance	Open lid and view sample from the top
Aroma	Open lid and bring sample close to the nose and smell
Texture-in-hand	Open lid, take a 1/3 rd part of the sample and feel between your fingers
Flavour	Open lid, take a 1/3 rd of the sample, chew and assess sample
Mouthfeel	Open lid, take a 1/3 rd of the sample, chew and assess sample
Aftertaste	Open lid, take 1/3 rd of sample and taste and assess aftertaste after 5 secs

Results

The following figures, presented as spider plots, summarize the sensory evaluation of the Fresh, Blanched, and Boiled kontomire leaves. They highlight differences in appearance, aroma, texture-in-hand, flavour, mouthfeel, and aftertaste, using mean intensity scores obtained from the quantitative descriptive analysis (QDA).

a. Appearance

Attributes marked with an asterisk (*) are significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 1: **Mean intensity scores for appearance attributes of fresh, boiled, and blanched Kontomire leaves (spider plot).**

The appearance results show clear differences among the Fresh, Blanched, and Boiled samples. The Fresh leaves were described as intense forest green colour, and they consistently recorded the lowest scores for most other appearance attributes. They looked drier, firmer, less glossy, and more intact compared to the processed samples. This makes the Fresh leaves significantly different from both Blanched and Boiled samples.

Blanching lightened the colour, while boiling produced an olive-green hue, showing that heat treatment changes the visual appearance of the leaves. Processing also introduced attributes such as juiciness, sogginess, and translucency, which were absent in the fresh samples.

Although the Boiled samples showed slightly higher mean scores for attributes like juiciness, sogginess, softness, and delicacy, these differences between Blanched and Boiled were not statistically significant. This means that, despite small variations in scores, both heat treatments affected the appearance in a similar way.

Overall, the Fresh leaves stood out as the most distinct, while Blanched and Boiled samples shared comparable appearance characteristics, with only minor, non-significant differences between them.

b. Aroma

Attributes marked with an asterisk (*) are significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 2: Mean intensity scores for aroma attributes of fresh, boiled, and blanched Kontomire leaves (spider plot).

The Fresh samples had the strongest and most distinctive aromas. They showed high intensities for grassy, watermelon rind, sugarcane, unripe pawpaw, plantain leaf, and other fresh leafy notes, indicating that the natural aroma of kontomire is most pronounced when the leaves are unprocessed.

Both Blanched and Boiled samples showed much lower aroma intensities, with a clear reduction in these fresh, green, and sweet notes. Processing introduced new aroma characteristics such as seashore, boiled maize, metallic, and fresh clam, reflecting the shift from raw to cooked-like aromas. Boiled yam aroma appeared in both heat-treated samples, but was slightly more intense in the blanched samples.

Overall, aroma decreased significantly with heat treatment. Fresh samples had the strongest leafy and green aromas, while Blanched and Boiled samples developed weaker, muted, and more cooked-like aromas due to loss of volatile fresh notes during heating.

c. Texture-in-hand

Attributes marked with an asterisk (*) are significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 3: **Mean intensity scores for texture-in-hand attributes of fresh, boiled, and blanched Kontomire leaves (spider plot).**

The texture-in-hand results show clear differences between the Fresh samples and the heat-treated samples. The Fresh samples generally had the lowest scores for soft and moist textures. They felt firmer and less moist when handled, which is expected since they have not undergone any heat treatment that could soften the leaves.

Both the Blanched and Boiled samples showed much higher intensities for attributes such as soft, moist, smooth, and rubbery. This means that heat treatment made the leaves softer and more pliable in the hand.

The fresh samples also had slightly higher values for rough bottom texture, while the boiled and blanched samples were smoother overall, again due to heat softening the leaf surfaces.

Overall, the results show that heat treatment significantly increases softness, moisture, smoothness, and rubberiness, with boiled samples showing the greatest effect. Fresh samples remain firmer and less moist, which reflects their intact structure.

d. Flavour, Mouthfeel, Aftertaste

Attributes marked with an asterisk (*) are significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 4: **Mean intensity scores for flavour, mouthfeel and aftertaste attributes of boiled and blanched Kontomire leaves (spider plot).**

The fresh kontomire leaves were not tasted due to their itchy and irritating nature when raw. Because of this, only the Blanched and Boiled samples provide meaningful sensory information.

Both blanched and boiled samples showed similar flavour intensities. They had a moderate kontomire-like flavour, showing that heat treatment helps release the characteristic taste of the leaves. Bitterness remained very low in both samples, meaning boiling or blanching did not introduce strong bitter notes. The heat-treated samples were soft, smooth, and easy to chew. They had a very low itchy sensation (both leaf and midrib), showing that heating greatly reduces the natural itchy feel that makes fresh kontomire unpleasant to taste. Boiled samples were slightly juicier and chewier than blanched samples, likely due to longer heat exposure. Aftertaste intensities were generally low for both blanched and boiled samples. They both showed a very low itchy after feel and bitter aftertaste and mild mouth residue, which

is normal for leafy vegetables. The low itchy and bitter aftertaste confirms that heat treatment effectively reduces the irritation associated with fresh kontomire.

CONCLUSION

Overall, the results show that blanching and boiling clearly modify the sensory characteristics of kontomire. Heat treatment softens the leaves, reduces their natural itchiness, and alters their colour, aroma, flavour, and texture. Although minor differences exist, blanched and boiled samples generally showed **similar sensory profiles** across appearance, aroma, mouthfeel, and aftertaste attributes. These findings highlight the role of thermal processing in shaping the sensory properties of kontomire and provide useful information for developing processed leafy vegetable products where consistent texture, colour, and flavour are important.

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